

LITERATURE REVIEW: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORKLOAD AND NURSES' WORK STRESS LEVEL IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT (ED)

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Abstract

Introduction: A nurse is someone who has the knowledge, skills and authority to provide nursing care to others based on the knowledge and tips they have within the limits of their authority. Nurses have the authority to provide holistic and professional health services for healthy and sick individuals, nurses are obliged to meet patient needs including bio-psycho-socio and spiritual. Nurses who work in emergency rooms are prone to stress due to high demands. The purpose of the literature review is to review the relationship between workload and work stress levels in nurses in the emergency room (ER). **Methods:** Literature review was conducted based on issue, methodology, similarities and further research proposals. A total of 8 quantitative studies were used for review. The population is all nurses who work in the emergency room and the sample used is part or all nurses who work in the emergency room. **Results:** Based on 8 studies, it was found that the heavier the workload of nurses, the higher the stress level of nurses working in the emergency room (ER). **Conclusion:** there is a relationship between nurses' workload and the level of stress in nurses in the emergency room (ER).

Keywords: stress, load, nurse, emergency department

1. INTRODUCTION

A nurse is someone who has the knowledge, skills and authority to provide nursing care to others based on the knowledge and tips they have within the limits of their authority. Nurses have the authority to provide holistic and professional health services for healthy and sick individuals, nurses are obliged to meet patient needs including bio-psycho-socio and spiritual. The nursing profession works in health services, both in government agencies and in private agencies. Intensive care in hospital services can be carried out in several places and one of them is in the emergency room. The Emergency Room, known as the Emergency Unit or Emergency Room Installation, is a place of work that is full of stress (Backe et al. 2012). Occupational risks are mostly experienced by nurses working in the Emergency Room (Hooper et al. 2010; Healy and Tyrrell 2011; Garcia-Izquierdo and Rios-Risquez 2012). The role of nurses in the Emergency Room is that nurses are always faced with stressors that vary from not understanding the origin, environment, crisis, need for knowledge of technology, accuracy of patient care, and the number of patients that cannot be predicted so that stress arises in the work performed by nurses.

Stress is a disturbance in the body and mind caused by changes and demands of life (Vincent Cornelli, in Jenita DT Donsu, 2017). According to Charles D. Spielberger, stress is external demands on a person such as objects in the environment or a stimulus that is objectively dangerous. Stress can also be interpreted as pressure, tension, unpleasant disturbances that come from outside a person (Jenita DT Donsu, 2017). In the work environment, high job demands can cause stress, especially services carried out in the emergency room where nurses are required to always be precise in action, friendly in service including with all diseases and bad symptoms that are certainly related to the lives of patients brought to the emergency room. The phenomenon of work stress has become a worldwide problem. This can be seen from the incidence of stress in the UK accounting for 385,000 cases, in Wales 11,000 to 26,000 cases (Health & Safety Executive, 2013). Of the forty cases of occupational stress, occupational stress in nurses ranks at the top and nurses can also have the opportunity to experience minor psychiatric disorders and depression (American national association for occupational Health, 2009).

From this explanation, stress in nurses really needs to be considered, because if a nurse experiences high stress it will have an impact on the quality of service. Basically, nurses are required to be able to provide services regularly and on time which must be supported by a friendly attitude, courtesy and willing to be patient and willing to take the time to listen to patient complaints by providing clear and understandable information. From this, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth assessment to determine the causes of work stress in nurses in the emergency room. Service management in the acute care room must prepare ways and methods in helping nurses not to experience work stress. Improved communication and support from superiors, clear work procedures, complete efficient administration will help nurses reduce their work stress. Based on this, it is important to know how the work stress of nurses in the emergency room. The research was taken to be analyzed through literature review.

2. METHODOLOGY

The method used in writing this article is systematic review, which is literature research that critically examines knowledge, ideas, or even findings in quality health journals, and is organized theoretically and methodologically for a particular topic (Lau & Kuziemy, 2016). The strategy used in the search for articles is to use research articles that match the topic on the Google Scholar database, this review is limited to searching literature in the last 5 years (2018-2023) using the following keywords "Nurse", "Emergency Room", and "Level", "Stress", "Work" with the determination of questions that follow the PICO technique. Where each question P is a sample with or without a nurse, I am a work stress intervention, C is a sample without work stress, O is the level of work stress. The inclusion criteria in this literature review were full-text articles.

Based on the results of data collection conducted, 9,950 articles and journals were identified, then the researchers conducted screening or removal of literature that was not included in the inclusion criteria for less than the last 5 years (2018-2023). The search results collected 7,080 articles as abstract candidates. Then the researcher discarded several articles that were irrelevant and did not match the desired variable criteria totaling 6,933 articles. The candidate study desired by the researcher was 147 articles. Then the deletion was carried out again in full review which the researcher wanted as many as 120 articles, so there were 27 articles in the review which were desired by the researcher. Then the researcher deleted back p = some articles that did not want to be included in the literature review as many as 19

articles. The desired article collected as many as 8 articles for review. Another relevant thing that the author used in obtaining journals about nurse stress in the emergency room. The author took all the research designs used in identifying nurse stress in the emergency room.

3. RESULTS

Author	Population	Objective of the study	Research methods	Results.
Relationship between Workload and Work Stress Level of Nurses in the Emergency Department Shieva Nur Azizah, Ahmad, Bunga Hidi Nopti (2019)	Population in this study is all nurses in public hospitals	To find out Relationship Workload with Job Stress Level Nurses in Emergency Room Installation Emergency Hospital Regency Tangerang	Using design Descriptive Collaboration With approach Cross Sectional.	Respondents who experiencing workload moderate and work stress moderate as many as 15 respondents (65.7%), stated that the workload was moderate and work stress heavy as many as 8 respondents (34.8%) and who stated that heavy workload and moderate work stress moderate as many as 2 respondents (11.8%), stated that the workload heavy workload and severe work stress as many as 15 respondents (88.2%)
Relationship Workload With Stress Level Nurse Room Intensive Care Unit and Emergency Room Nonik Eka Martyastuti, Isrofah, Khalilatun Janah (2019)	Population in this study is all nurses in public hospitals Siaga Medika Pematang	To find out Relationship Workload With Stress Level Nurse Room Intensive Care Unit and Emergency Room	Quantitative associative analytic with approach Cross Sectional	Respondents who have light workload and mild stress level there are 15 (33.3%) respondents, who have light workload and moderate stress level of moderate stress were 9 (20,0%)
Determinants of Job Stress in Emergency Department Nurses Emergency and Intensive Care Unit Nurses at Dr. Rasidin	The population was all nurses in the emergency room and ICU at the Dr. Rasidin Regional General Hospital in Padang.	to determine the factors associated with work stress in emergency room nurses and ICU at RSUD dr. Rasidin Padang	quantitative with a cross sectional approach	Research results the results showed that 51.5% of nurses experienced moderate work stress, 51.5% had a heavy workload, 63.6% experienced an unfavorable work environment, 60.6% felt high role conflict, 51.5% old age (≥ 36

<p>Regional General Hospital</p> <p>Fitriyani, Miftahul Jannah, Veri Wardi (2022)</p>				<p>years) and 54.5% new tenure (< 10 years).</p>
<p>Factors Associated with Nurses' Job Stress Emergency Room and Intensive Care Unit.</p> <p>Ressy Herlia, Rin Muthia Zuhra, Reni Zulfitri (2022)</p>	<p>whole nurses who work in the emergency room and ICU of Arifin Achmad Hospital Pekanbaru.</p>	<p>to determine factors associated with job stress in emergency room nurses and ICU</p>	<p>Design Descriptive research design with a cross-sectional approach</p>	<p>Based on the results of the research conducted, the frequency distribution of frequency of nurses who experience work stress in the Emergency Room of Arifin Achmad Hospital is 71.4% experiencing severe stress. While in the Intensive Care Unit room of Arifin Achmad Hospital, 57.1% experienced mild stress.</p>
<p>Relationship between Nurses' Workload and Work Stress Level in the Emergency Room and ICU Hospital Prof. Dr. Soekandar Mojokerto Year 2023</p> <p>Aldy Wicaksono, M. Arwani, Ety Diana. (2023)</p>	<p>Population This study is an executive nurse in the emergency room (IGD) and intensive care unit (ICU) who has worked for a year or more.</p>	<p>The purpose of This study is to analyze the relationship between nurses' workload and work stress in the emergency room. And ICU Prof. Dr. Soekandar Hospital.</p>	<p>This type of research uses quantitative analytic design Crosectional</p>	<p>Univariate analysis shows most of the nurses' workload is 37.5% heavy workload, 30% moderate workload, and 32.5% light workload. And Work Stress most nurses with mild work stress are 50%, moderate stress 25% and severe 25%. moderate stress 25% and severe 25%. As well as bivariate analysis using the chi square test that $p = 0.00$ (p value < 0.05) which means there is a relationship between nurses' workload and work stress in the Emergency Room.</p>
<p>Factors Associated with Nurses' Job Stress Level in the Emergency Room Dr. Ramelan Surabaya</p> <p>Nety Mawarda</p>	<p>Population in this study are Nurses in the Emergency Room of Dr. Ramelan Naval Hospital Surabaya as many as 45 people.</p>	<p>The purpose of this study is to analyze the factors associated with the level of work stress of nurses in the emergency room Hospital Dr. Ramelan Surabaya.</p>	<p>This research design uses descriptive research methods.</p>	<p>Nurses aged 26-35 years old almost half of them experienced moderate nurse work stress, those male gender almost half experienced mild nurse work stress, with 3-5 years of service more than half experienced moderate nurse work stress and</p>

Hatmanti, Novi Puspitasari, Chilyatiz Zahroh, Priyo Mukti Pribadi Winoto. (2023)				who have a moderate nurse workload most of them experienced moderate work stress?
Influence Workload on Satisfaction Nurse Work Satisfaction With Mediation of Stress Work Laily Nurida Safitri, Mardi Astutik (2019)	Population in this study is all nurses in Hospital Unipdu Medika Jombang	to find out Effect of Workload Against Job Satisfaction Nurse with Mediation of Stress Work	quantitative with using method survey	Working conditions have a negative and significant on Stress Work Stress of Nurses in the Hospital. Work Stress partially mediates between Workload to Job Satisfaction Nurses at the Hospital Unipdu Medika Jombang
Factor Analysis Which Related with Stress Nurse Work Stress Matilda Lantaran Sari, Luh Putu Ruliati, Erny Erawati Pua Upa (2019)	Population in this study is all nurses in Hospital Naimata Mental Hospital Kupang	to find out Factor Analysis Which Related with Stress Nurse Work Stress at Naimata Mental Hospital Naimata Mental Hospital Kupang Year 2019	survey analytics with design Cross Sectional design Study	shows that together the independent variables are related with work stress nurses. with a coefficient of determination coefficient of 62,5%

- 3.1 In the first article, research conducted by Shieva Nur Azizah Ahmad, Bunga Hidi, Nopti (2019) at the Emergency Department of Tangerang Regency Hospital using a Colleration Descriptive design with a Cross Sectional approach explained that the heavier the nurse's workload, the higher the nurse's stress. Conversely, the lower the nurse's workload, the lower the nurse's stress level.
- 3.2 In the second article, research conducted by Nonik Eka Martyastuti, Isrofah, Khalilatun Janah (2019) at Siaga Medika Pemasang Hospital with a quantitative associative analytic research design with a cross-sectional approach explained that the heavier the nurse's workload, the higher the nurse's stress. Conversely, the lower the nurse's workload, the lower the nurse's stress level.
- 3.3 In the third article, research conducted by Fitriyani, Miftahul Jannah, Veri Wardi (2022) at Dr. Rasidin Padang Regional General Hospital with a quantitative research design with a cross sectional approach explained that the causes of work stress are heavy workload, poor work environment, feeling high role conflict, being over 36 years old, and a new working period of less than 10 years.
- 3.4 In the fourth article, research conducted by Ressay Herlia, Ririn Muthia Zuhra, Reni Zulfitri (2022) at RSUD Arifin Achmad Pekanbaru with descriptive research

- design with a cross sectional approach found that the distribution of nurses who experienced severe stress was more in the ER room compared to the ICU room.
- 3.5 In the fifth article, research conducted by Aldy Wicaksono, M. Arwani, Ety Diana. (2023) in the Emergency Room and ICU of Prof. Dr. Soekandar Hospital with the type of research using quantitative analytics with a Crosectional design explaining that there is a relationship between nurse workload and work stress.
 - 3.6 In the sixth article, research conducted by Nety Mawarda Hatmanti, Novi Puspitasari, Chilyatiz Zahroh, Priyo Mukti Pribadi Winoto. (2023) in the emergency room of Dr. Ramelan Surabaya Hospital with this research design using descriptive research methods explaining that nurses who have moderate nurse workload mostly experience moderate work stress.
 - 3.7 In the seventh article, research conducted by Laily Nurida Safitri, Mardi Astutik (2019) at Unipdu Medika Jombang Hospital with a quantitative type of research using survey methods explained that working conditions have a negative and significant effect on Nurses' Work Stress in Hospitals. Work Stress partially mediates between Workload and Nurse Job Satisfaction.
 - 3.8 In the eighth article, research conducted by Lantaran Sari, Luh Putu Ruliati, Erny Erawati Pua Upa (2019) at Naimata Kupang Mental Hospital using an analytical survey with a Cross Sectional Study design explained that the factors that influence nurses' work stress are workload, interpersonal relationships and work safety.

4. DISCUSSION

Nurse workload is a dimension of all activities or activities carried out by a nurse while on duty in a health service unit to provide nursing care carefully, quickly, precisely and within a certain time (Vanchapo, 2020). Nurses are required to complete work within a certain time and excessive workload will cause stress in nurses so that it allows nurses to not be able to perform nursing care services optimally, effectively and efficiently because the physical and cognitive abilities of nurses are reduced (Wijono, 2018).

According to Nursalam (2016), workload in the room is not always stressful for nurses, workload will cause stress if the amount of workload is not proportional to the physical abilities, experience and expertise and time available to nurses. Each nurse has a normal ability to complete the tasks assigned to him, besides that workload is important to identify potential causes of stress in the hospital, because stress will befall nurses, and each nurse has a different way of withstanding stress depending on the length, type and frequency of stress experienced. This is reinforced by research research (Sari et.al 2019) that nurse workload standards always have to be in accordance with patient needs-oriented nursing care. To produce effective and efficient services, a match between the availability of nurses and the existing workload is sought.

Research conducted by (Safitri et al., 2019) which shows the effect of workload on nurses' work stress where the cause of work stress is excessive workload so that it takes more time to complete the job. This research is in line with research conducted by (Sari et al., 2019) which says that work stress in nurses is influenced by heavy workloads where between long working hours can trigger work stress caused by fatigue. This shows that working 2 shifts (16 hours) more than regular working hours causes negative results for patients, nurses and the hospital itself. Analysis of nurses' workload that causes stress can be seen from various

aspects, one of which is the working time used to do their duties whether it is in accordance with the working hours that take place every day with the workload given (Gunawan, 2016).

According to the researcher, the heavier the nurse's workload, the higher the nurse's stress level, especially nurses who work in the ER room, as for some factors that trigger the patient's stress level besides workload, namely a poor work environment, feeling high role conflict, being over 36 years old, and a new working period of less than 10 years.

5. CONCLUSION

There is a relationship between nurses' workload and the level of stress in nurses in the emergency room (ER). The heavier the nurse's workload, the higher the nurse's stress level, especially nurses who work in the ER room.

6. REFERENCES

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